

THE USE OF NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

this article examines the role of Information Technology in education, the quality of lessons through the use of Information Technology in teaching exercises and the increasing interest of young people in the IT field, as well as the advantages of multimedia tools in education.

The modern world level of development of information and Communication Technologies is such that the creation of a national system compatible with the integration of the infrastructures of the world information space and the National Information and computing network in the Republic is an important factor of the efficiency of the national economy, Management, Science and education. These problems are quite complex and at the same time relevant for our republic. The results of the implementation of the economic, structural and other changes currently being implemented are also related to how and within what terms the problems related to informatization in the Republic are solved. The creation of e-learning tools in Educational Sciences further enhances the possibility of using modern information and communication technologies in the teaching of these

subjects. This, in turn, is the main factor in the deep acquisition of students' knowledge in these disciplines, which increases the quality and effectiveness of Education. The implementation of such efforts creates an opportunity to further accelerate the wide application of modern pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process, to arm professors and teachers with advanced pedagogical knowledge and technologies, to improve their skills, to deeply study the experience of foreign higher education institutions, and to introduce effective methods and tools in them into our national education system. Multimedia is a modern information technology, which is developing proudly. Its distinguishing signs include the following: a variety of types of Information: traditional (text, tables, decorations, etc.), original (speech, music, excerpts from video films, TV shows,

animation, etc.), integrating types into one software product. Such an integration means that different devices of recording and displaying information, work at a certain time, in contrast to text and graphics that are static by their nature, audio and video signals are considered only at a certain interval of time.

MAIN PART

Teaching students on the basis of Multimedia tools has the following advantages:

- 1) there is the possibility of deeper and more perfect reduction of the given materials;
- 2) increased enthusiasm for close communication with new areas of Education:
- 3) as a result of the reduction in educational time, achieve the opportunity to save time;
- 4) the acquired knowledge is preserved long in the memory of the person, and the ability to cope in practice when finding it is necessary. Informatics and information technology as a fundamental science is engaged in the development of a methodology for restoring the provision of management processes in terms of information with the desired objects on the basis of Computer Information Systems. There is also such an opinion that one of the main tasks of science is to determine what information systems are, what position they occupy, what structure they should have, how they work, what laws are specific to them. In the field of Informatics in Europe, the following main scientific directions can be distinguished: the development of a network structure, the production of a computer integrated process, economic and medical informatics, social insurance and environmental

Informatics, professional information systems. The emergence of Multimedia system has led to the emergence of revolutionary changes in many professional fields such as education, science, art, computer training, advertising, technology, medicine, mathematics, business, scientific research.

Although the idea of using computers in the educational system appeared much earlier, the use of Information Technology in all areas of the educational system began to be introduced into practice literally after the appearance of computers equipped with multimedia devices. The use of Multimedia tools in education provides an opportunity for:

- * ensuring the humanization of Education;
- development of personal qualities of the educator (self-assimilation, thirst for knowledge, Independent Education, self-education, self-improvement skills, creative abilities, ability to apply the acquired knowledge to practice, interest in learning, attitude to Labor);

Multimedia tools can be used in harmony with various educational trends (styles) and can be used by individuals who have different mental and age-related characteristics of learning as well as cognitive perception: some educators enjoy learning and mastering knowledge through direct reading, others through hearing perception, others through viewing (videographs). Interactive multimedia technologies provide an unconventional convenience to the educator with academic need. In particular, it provides for an increase in phonological skills and reading skills, as well as their visual assimilation of information, in education recipients who have a defect in the sense of hearing. And in those who have limited speech and

physical abilities, it allows the use of tools based on their individual needs. Multimedia tools are an effective and promising weapon (instruments) of teaching and it is to provide the teacher with a wider range of information massively than traditional source of information; visually and harmoniously,

the use of not only text, graphics, schemes, but also sound, animations, video, etc.; creates the opportunity to select types of information in a sequence according to the level of acceptance (perception) and logical learning of the educators.

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